

Application of Machine Learning for Road Safety Modeling of Selected South-West Highway in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Road crash prediction has proven to be an effective means of improving highway safety. In recent years, machine learning (ML) models have been embraced as efficient for the prediction of road accident frequency. This study applied two machine learning models for the prediction of road accident occurrence on selected South-West highway in Nigeria. Accident data were obtained for the period of 10 years from 2013 to 2022 from the Federal Road Safety Commission (FRSC) of Nigeria on the road under study and the traffic operations were determined on site using manual counting and stopwatch approach. Machine Learning (ML) models including Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) were also used as the statistical model for safety prediction of the highway with consideration to identified contributing factors. The performance of the models was compared for both training and testing dataset using coefficient of determination (R^2), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The study showed consistency and effective performance in both ML models with R^2 of 0.99 in SVM, 0.97 and XGBoost for training data, also 0.93 in SVM and 0.76 in XGBoost testing data. ML models are also easy and fast to implement. The result of this study supports the use of ML as a predictive tool for road safety evaluation. The knowledge attained from this study will benefit transportation planners, engineers, and policymakers to implement effective measures aimed at reducing the crash occurrence, thereby enhancing overall transportation safety and efficiency.

Keywords: Machine learning modelling, SVM, XGBoost, Road safety prediction.

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INTRODUCTION

Road crashes has been identified as the eight leading cause of death in developing country such as Nigeria [4]. Road crash prediction is an essential aspect of road safety influencing, transportation efficiency, traffic management, and infrastructural planning [5]. Crash prediction models also referred to as safety performance functions (SPFs) are often used in highway safety analyses for numerous applications including identifying the relationship between explanatory or screening variables [9,20]. The variables could be factors influencing road crash occurrence such as human, road, traffic, vehicular, environmental factors. Another important application of crash prediction models consists of identification of hazardous sites and relating the safety performance of different highway design alternatives for hypothetical scenarios in present or future facilities [3]. This is dependent on the objectives of study, they can also be used in before-and-after studies. Road transportation is an essential means of mobility in today's modern development [18]. For smooth flow of daily activities, travels, and businesses, the safety of the facilities is critical in planning, designing and construction. Several factors contribute to road crash occurrence which makes it complex to analyse. Human factors including speed violation, dangerous driving, wrongful overtaking and driving on influence. Road factor including design characteristics (radius of curvature, gradient of road, pavement width, shoulder width and road intersection) are essential for the regulation of road safety. Traffic factor such as traffic flow and traffic speed are all influence on safety, visibility, and comfort [10,30]. Mechanical factors (brake failure and vehicle functions) and environmental Factors (weather condition). The complexity and multidimensional relationship between road crash and the contributing factors highlight the necessary consideration for effective model for road safety prediction [8,17].

Effective and accurate prediction of road crash enhance traffic efficiency and reduce accident risks [15,16]. In order for accurate prediction of crashes, an efficient crash prediction model is required. A model that fits the data adequately, without over-fitting or under-fitting of dataset [33]. Highway safety researchers usually compare several statistical models based on goodness of fit to determine the best model [20,24,32]. Recent research focuses on developing models solely used for predicting road crashes [6,9,22]. In line with the new wave of research activity, very few existing methods can be used to efficiently predict road crashes [3]. For those available, they can sometimes be complex to implement and include limitations [3]. Thus, there is a need to examine other methods for prediction of road crashes frequency.

The objective of this study is to evaluate the application of Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) to predict of road crash frequency on two major highways namely Akure-Ilesha (two lane highway) and Sagamu-Lagos (multi-lane highway) in southwest Nigeria. The dataset used for evaluation are road traffic operations were evaluated onsite, and other accident factors were determined from historical data collected from the Federal Road Safety Cooperation (FRSC) of Nigeria for 10 years study period. Regression model was also used to investigate the relationships between the dependent variable (road crash frequency) and the independent variables (human, road, traffic, mechanical and environmental factors) [1].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Traditional statistical methods such as linear or multilinear regression have been employed by researchers to determine the relation between road crash frequency and selected variables [24,27]. [27] developed accident prediction models for the Akure-Ondo two lane highway, utilizing multiple linear regressions. The model utilized the number of people killed, people injured, and people involved as the independent variables. Linear regression often exhibits larger discrepancies between the observed and the predicted crash frequency [20]. However, Poisson and negative binomial regression models have been employed by transportation researchers for road crash prediction. Negative binomial regression model produce narrower confidence intervals compared to Poisson regression model [17,25]. It is an extension of Poisson regression, sharing the same mean structure while adding features accounting for over-dispersion, random, discrete, and non-negative nature of road crash [8,29,37]. [13] employed negative binomial regression model for the prediction of motorway crash on both rural and urban motorway segments. The model incorporated non-

behavioral contributing factors such as traffic conditions, geometric and operational characteristics of the road, and weather conditions [2]. [25] utilize negative binomial regression model to predict road crash rates for Ghana roads.

Recently, machine learning models are employed for the prediction of road crash on highway and the performance are compared with the traditional models [11,14,32,33]. [32] and [14] investigated the efficiency of SVM in predicting road crash frequency at traffic analysis zones for rural highway and compared the performance of SVM with fixed-random effect negative binomial models. Other machine learning including artificial neural network (ANN), Bayesian Neural Network (BNN), random forest (RF), support vector machine (SVM), decision tree (DT), logistic regression (LR), adaptive boosting (AdaBoost), extreme gradient boost (XGBoost) and Categorical boost (CatBoost) [19,21,28,35]. [35] utilized XGBoost in prediction of road traffic accident severity considering several influencing factors. [33] applied three different machine learning model including SVM, RF and DT in the prediction of road crash and compared the performance of the models with negative binomial regression. [11] also compared the performance of three machine learning algorithms (LR, DT and RF) in predicting road accident severity.

Overall, the literature suggests that machine learning models provide fast and more accurate predictions superior to traditional regression models. Reliable machine learning model for crash frequency prediction should show an acceptable range between overfitting and underfitting of training data. Therefore, machine learning models are promising tool for road crash prediction and could be employed.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology for prediction of road traffic safety in this study is divided into four main steps: (1) Data Collection, (2) Data Processing (3) Machine learning Models and (4) Model Performance Evaluation Criteria. Figure 1 shows the conceptual flow chart of the methodology of the research.

Figure 1. Conceptual Work Flow Diagram

Data Collection

The data collected for the study focuses on two major highway categories in Nigeria which are the two lane and multi-lane highways linking five major states in the southwest region of the country namely Ondo, Osun, Oyo, Ogun and Lagos. Figure 2 shows the map of study area.

1. Two lane Highway – (Owo-Akure and Akure-Ilesha) and

2. Multilane Highway – (Ilesha- Ibadan and Sagamu-Lagos).

Accident data for the highway under study were obtained from the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) of each state command for observation period of 10years from 2014 to 2023. The contributing factors including human factors (Over speeding, wrongful overtaking, traffic control violation, Use of phone while driving, fatigue), environmental (rainfall, harsh weather) and mechanical (burst tyre, brake failure, malfunction of vehicle) were extracted from the data. The traffic factors including speed and volume were determined on site [5]. Stopwatch approach was utilized to compute the spot speed of passenger vehicles and Traffic count was also employed to determine the number of vehicles using the facilities. The numbers of vehicles were counted at each location for one week at 12 hours daily to compute the ADT.

Figure 2. Map of Study Area

Data Processing

The collected data were processed and cleaned in order to remove duplicate entries, handling missing values, and correcting inconsistencies from the dataset. The performance of model depends on the relevance input parameters, therefore irrelevance parameters introduce noise or bias to the model [35,36]. Python programming was used for the analysis with the total of 2550 datasets. The datasets were splinted into training (70%) and testing (30%) sets. Table 1 illustrates the statistical description of independent variables.

Table 1. Statistics Attributes of Independent Variables

Variable	Min	max	Mean	Variance	S.D
Human Factors					
Speed Violation (SV)	40.09	100	64.3	195.09	13.437
Wrongful Overtaking(WO)	10	250	343.456	632.32	42.65
Loss of Control (LC)	42	122	97.67	530.56	23.03
Use of Phone (UP)	0	17	4.42	10.45	3.65

Fatigue (FA)	0	150	143.227	469.68	21.672
Driving under Influence (DI)	0	53	23.227	125.87	11.72
Traffic Factors					
Traffic Volume (TV)	7344	9126	8159.7	614890	784.2
Operating Speed (V_{85})	45.8	120	97.67	181.2	13.45
Mechanical Factors					
Burst of Tyre (BT)	0	100	99.227	469.68	21.672
Brake Failure (BF)	10	250	343.456	632.32	42.65
Vehicle Fault (VF)	0	41	12.74	51.43	9.88
Environmental Factor					
Weather Condition (WC)	0	17	4.52	10.43	3.75

Machine Learning Models

Support Vector Machine

Support vector machine (SVM) is a subdivision of machine learning model that predicts variables which involves both linear and non-linear functions for classification and regression problems [38]. It was developed by [39] following Cover's theorem (1965). The linear function expressed in Equation 1 can be reframed in high dimensional variables to symbolize non-linear relation between the dependent variable (x_i) and the independent variable (y_i). This study used Equation 2 which indicates the optimized linear functions. The SVM type adopted for this study is used for regression problems and is known as Support Vector Regression (SVR).

$$y_i = f(x_i) = (a, b(x_i)) + c \quad (1)$$

$$\min Z(w, \varepsilon, \xi_i, \xi_{ii}) = \frac{1}{2} w^T + C \left[v\varepsilon + \frac{1}{N} \sum (\xi_i + \xi_{ii}) \right] \quad (2)$$

Subject to

$$w^T \Phi(x(i)) + b - y(i) \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

$$y(i) - w^T \Phi(x(i)) + b - y(i) \leq \varepsilon + \xi_i, \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

$$\xi_i, \xi_{ii} \geq 0 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, n$$

Where; ξ_i and ξ_{ii} are slack variables, C is a regularization parameter, and v is a second parameter for each $x(i)$, the allowable error is ε . Function $\Phi(x(i))$ to linearize the nonlinear relationship between $x(i)$ and $y(i)$. Assuming the input training variables $x(i)$ for $1, \dots, n$ and training variable $y(i)$ for $1, \dots, n$. w and b are model parameters. w is optimization problem solution, ε_i is model residuals ($\varepsilon_i = y_i - f(x_i)$), [7] further posited that "the constant C determines the amount up to which deviations from ε are tolerated and C which is always positive is the penalty parameter on the training error. Practically, selection of the kernel function $K(x_i, x_j) = \phi(x_i)^T \cdot \phi(x_j)$ is enough for training the SVM".

Extreme Gradient Boosting

The Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBOOST) algorithm was implemented in this research to investigate the relationship between highway crash frequency and identified factors contributing to the occurrence. Extreme boost was selected due to its capacity to generate precise and dependable predictions and its exceptional reliability in managing structured data. [19] and [35] described XGBoost as powerful machine learning algorithm that improves prediction accuracy through a boosting framework. The fundamental of XGBoost as developed by [12], the model builds multiple decision trees sequentially, minimizing errors by adjusting weights and optimizing loss functions. The model predicts the crash frequency (\hat{y}_i) from ensembled decision trees by K additive function expressed in Equation 3. The Objective function of the model expressed in Equation 4 combines the loss function which measures the model fitness and the regularizer, this is to control overfitting

complexity in the model. The regularizer also includes two penalties; penalty of tree numbers and leaf weights. The values assigned to the terminal nodes of each tree are the leaf weight representing the predicted output of samples in the leaf [35]. These penalties are determined using Taylor's second order approach in Equation 5 and gradient descent to optimize the objective function. Equation 6 shows the computed regularizer.

$$\hat{Y} = \Phi(x_i) = \sum_{n=1}^n f_k(x_i), f \quad (3)$$

$$Obj(\Phi) = \sum l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + \sum \Omega(f_n) \quad (4)$$

$$f(x + \Delta x) = f(x) + f^1(x)\Delta x + \frac{1}{2}f^{11}(x)\Delta x^2 \quad (5)$$

$$Obj(\Phi) = \sum \{l(y_i, \hat{y}_i) + g_i f(x_i) + \frac{1}{2} h_i f^2(x_i)\} + \sum \Omega(f_n) \quad (6)$$

Where: \hat{y}_i is the target predicted variable, y_i is the independent variable of computed operating speed, x_i are the dependent variables selected geometric features, n are the numbers of features, f_k , is the tree structure with leaf score, f is the space of trees, Ω is the regularizer and g_i, h_i are the optimization value.

Model Performance Evaluation Criteria

The models performance were evaluated and compared using some criteria such as coefficient of determination (R^2) expressed in Equation (7), root mean square error (RMSE) in Equation (8), Mean Absolute error (MAE) Equation (9) and the average value of observations computed with Equation (10).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (7)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (8)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{y} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \quad (10)$$

Where; n is the number of observations, y_i is the actual value of the i th observation, \hat{y}_i is the predicted value of the i th observed and \bar{y} is the average value of observations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Considering the interaction of various factors on the road crash frequency, the influential roles of these factors are obtained and analyzed through the inference results of the prediction model from the location, correlation heat map and factors sensitivity analysis. The performance of the models

were also compared. These results can provide insight, direction and countermeasures for traffic safety management [31,34].

Accident Occurrence and Location Survey

Figure 4(a) shows the relationship between accident occurrence and road type location. Accident are more frequent along the multilane highway compared to the two lane due to the traffic demand in the location. Figure 4(b) shows that the causes of crash along the routes are categorized into four main factors from the accident data gotten from FRSC which are human factor, mechanical factor, traffic factor and environmental factor. Human factors account for 70% of the crashes on the highways including speed violation (SV), loss of control (LC), wrongful overtaking (WO), use of phone (UP) and fatigue (FA) while 20% of the crashes were caused by mechanical factors including brake failure, burst of tyre or vehicle fault, traffic factors including vehicle operating speed V_{85} and Average daily traffic (ADT) accounts for 15% road crash and environmental factors or weather condition influence of 4% on crashes occurrence along the highway.

(a) Relationship between Accident Occurrence and Location

(b) Factors Contributing to Accident Occurrence

Figure 4. Accident Occurrence to Location and Contributing Factors

Model Correlation Analysis of Accident Occurrence and Contributing Factors

The importance and correlation contribution of each variable evaluated indicates the interplay of the features highlighted to the prediction of accident occurrence. Figure 5(a) indicates the degree of importance of the variables to accident (crash) occurrence prediction. The importance were sorted according to the mean value from the absolute value obtained from the degree of impact on the target variable. The diagram illustrates traffic volume (TV) as most influential parameter with the highest global impact. Vehicle brake failure (BF), Operating Speed (V_{85}), Speed violation (SV) are also important contributing parameter to accident occurrence along the highway. This findings are

consistent with [26]. Lesser contributing impart are recorded in vehicle failure (VF), use of phone (UP) and fatigue (FA) according to the model.

The thermal also known as the heat map in Figure 5(b) illustrates the correlation among each dependent variables and the independent variables using the six (6) highlighted important parameters. The variables are sorted from large to small according to the correlation coefficient of the independent variables to the dependent variable Accident Occurrence (AO). The correlation sorted the dependent variables to independent variable in the following arrangement as indicated in the figure; (1) Brake Failure- (2) Traffic Volume- (3) Operating Speed- (4) Speed Violation- (5) Loss of Control- and (6) Wrongful Overtaking. This is reasonable because brake failure can lead to driver's loss of control, which could in turn causes multiple accident occurrence in area with large traffic volume [11,23].

Correlation interrelation of dependent variable to variable in the heat map, Brake Failure (BF) and Speed Violation (SV) correlate with coefficient (0.98) in prediction of accident occurrence indicating high significant impact. [26] also found brake failure as a significant parameter influencing road crashes occurrence. Traffic Volume (TV) and Operation Speed (V_{85}) strongly correlate with coefficient (0.93), Loss of Control (LC) and Wrongful Overtaking (WO), Traffic Volume (TV) and Brake Failure (BF), also Traffic Volume (TV) and Loss of Control (LC) correlate significantly to each other with coefficient (0.76, 0.63 and 0.6) respectively. This is indeed practical due to the interrelationship between all the parameter evaluated and the contributing factor to accident occurrence. These relationships between TV, LC, BF, WO, V_{85} and SV are consistent with [22,35,36] findings.

In contrast, speed violation and wrongful overtaking, loss of control and speed violation, wrongful overtaking and speed violation were found to be statistically insignificant, with negative coefficients lesser than -0.4 in each case.

(a) Importance of Dependent Variables

(b) Correlation Heat Map of Variables

Figure 5. Variable Importance and Correlation Heat Map

Performance Evaluation of Models

Table 3 shows the summary of the result of performance evaluation conducted on all the models. The ML models performance were compared for both training and testing dataset fitness of data and accuracy of prediction. From the result, SVM outperformed XGBoost in both training and testing dataset. The coefficient of determination (R^2) was 0.9985 tending to 1 which indicates 99.9% data fitting in the training dataset while XGBoost has good data fitting R^2 value of 0.8453 indicating 84.5% fitness. The root mean square error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute error (MAE) of SVM recorded the lowest value indicating better transferability and less prediction error in the training and testing data. Overall, the performance evaluation suggest ML models for accident frequency predictions with better goodness of fit and accuracy [19,33].

Table 3. Performance Evaluation Comparison

Model	R^2	RMSE	MAE
Training Set			
SVM	0.9985	0.9784	0.9702
XGBoost	0.8453	8.0947	6.1866
Testing Set			
SVM	0.9315	6.2399	4.9789
XGBoost	0.7696	9.4419	8.3223

CONCLUSIONS

This study assessed the application of machine learning models in the prediction of road crash occurrence in selected highway of SouthWest, Nigeria. The following findings are highlighted from the research,

- a. From the preliminary accident data check on the selected southwest roads, it indicated accident occurs more frequently on multilane highway compared with two lane highway. This is influenced by human factors, traffic factors, mechanical factors and environmental factors.
- b. Similarly, the machine learning (ML) model correlation and importance of variables indicates brake failure, traffic volume, operating speed, speed Violation, loss of control and wrongful overtaking as importance features contributing to traffic accident occurrence along highways and significant parameters in the prediction of road crash occurrence.
- c. The performance evaluation of the machine learning models are satisfactory and effective for the prediction of road crash occurrence with good data fitness and predictive accuracy.
- d. Although, ML-Based models application provided positive results in the prediction of road crash occurrence, it is suggested that further research should be explored to evaluate the models using new dataset across other jurisdiction. Regulatory rules to enforce speed limit to reduce and to checkmate over speeding by the drivers and regular monitoring of road conditions, traffic patterns, and safety metrics is essential to identify emerging issues promptly and adjust interventions accordingly. This measures are suggested for better performance on Nigeria highways.

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